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[Anticholinergic, antimicrobial, and anticancer perspectives of atropine: A mini-review](#)

Abstract:

Atropine metabolite as a tropane alkaloid is mainly applied as anticholinergic medication. Other therapeutic activities such as anticancer and antimicrobial effects have been found for this metabolite. Several side effects such as blurred vision, dryness of the mouth, dry eyes, confusion, photophobia, dizziness, tachycardia, fatigue, flushing, palpitations, urinary hesitance or retention, headache, constipation, nausea, and vomiting have been identified for this bioactive compound. Therefore, reduction of these side effects is critical to obtain effective therapeutic activities of atropine in physiological conditions. Application of micro and nano formulations and combination therapy may be desirable strategies. This mini-review has attempted to discuss both advantages and disadvantages of these novel strategies based on recent advances.

Keywords: Atropine, True alkaloids, Proto alkaloids, Tropane ring, Anticholinergic activity, Effective formulations

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